

iImagine

D5.3 Final periodical assessment of Imaging VA services

Abstract

The report provides the third-year usage statistics and assessment of the 5 thematic, AI-powered image analysis services provided under virtual access in WP5.

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<https://www.egi.eu/project/imagine/>

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D5.3 Final periodical assessment of Imaging VA services			
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Executive summary

This report provides an assessment at the end of M36 of the WP5 installations provided by the iMagine project under the Virtual Access (VA) mechanism. This assessment is based on the metrics collected from the WP5 installations which have been deployed and become operational during the project.

WP5 installations are the Imaging Analysis Services set up by the 5 mature marine imaging use cases from the WP3 development activities:

1. Marine litter assessment service
2. Zooscan taxonomic identification service
3. Marine ecosystem monitoring service
4. Oil spill detection service
5. Flowcam phytoplankton identification

Originally, all five mature use cases were planned to be fully deployed and operational at M24, meeting milestone M5.4. However, in practice this applied only for two services: UC1 – Marine litter assessment service and namely UC5 – Flowcam phytoplankton identification service. The other three use cases reached production stage a few months later, mostly in September – October 2024. These delays were experienced because user interface and module developments, as well as AI model training took longer than expected.

The report gives the Virtual Access (VA) metrics for the last period (M25 – M36) and compares with the previous period (M13 – M24). The metrics highlight diverse levels of engagement across the 5 services:

1. The Marine litter assessment service recorded 26 users across 3 countries who processed 95 images.
2. The ZooScan service had 9 users processing 1,150 scans.
3. The Marine ecosystem monitoring service showed diverse uptake: EMSO–Obsea processed 1.3 million images, EMSO–SmartBay annotated over 10,000, and EMSO–Azores supported 6 user groups across 6 countries.
4. The Oil spill detection service supported 80 users who processed 172 images.
5. The Flowcam phytoplankton identification service served 129 unique users and processed 2.26 million images, expanding to 10 countries, driven by international collaborations and workshops.

Across the five WP5 services, some metrics fell short of their targets due to a combination of technical and domain-specific factors. The most pervasive issue was the delayed availability of mature user interfaces, with three services only reaching full production in September–October 2024, significantly compressing the time available for external onboarding. Beyond timing, some services faced inherent domain barriers: the Marine litter service required specialised drone infrastructure that limited its eligible user base,

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while ZooScan onboarding remained restricted to technically advanced users capable of API integration.

To address these shortfalls, iMagine launched the iMagine Webinar Series in January 2025 featuring live demonstrations of all five thematic services by their respective owners, with recordings made publicly available at www.imagine-ai.eu. The series was complemented by presentations, posters, demos and workshops at international conferences, and hands-on training events, most visibly benefiting the Flowcam phytoplankton service, which grew from 7 to 129 users and expanded to 10 countries. Further outreach was supported through open dataset repositories on Zenodo and SeaNoe, and the availability of pre-trained models on the iMagine Marketplace, collectively lowering technical barriers and fostering a broader international user community.

1 Introduction

Virtual Access (VA) is a financial instrument to reimburse access provisioning costs to access providers. This instrument is provided by the European Commission to increase the sharing of research infrastructures and services that otherwise would not be available to international user groups.

In VA, the services – also called “installations” – must be made available ‘free of charge at the point of use’ for European or International researchers. VA access is open and free access to services through communication networks to resources needed for research, without selecting the researchers to whom access is provided.

Virtual Access to services of the iImagine catalogue applies to the following 2 categories:

- AI platform and compute infrastructure services in WP4
- Imaging data and analysis service in aquatic sciences in WP5

This document provides Virtual Access metrics and a comparison between the 2nd (Sep 2023 – Aug 2024) and 3rd year (Sept 2024 – Aug 2025) of the project. In practice, two use cases were taken into production in the 2nd year, UC1 – Marine litter assessment service which then reached near-operational stage, and UC5 – Flowcam phytoplankton identification, which then reached full operational stage. All other mature use cases took a few months more to get into full production, mostly in September – October 2024.

1.1 Installations

Within iImagine, 5 installations are part of Virtual Access Work Package 5. These installations support the baseline computing infrastructure of iImagine as part of the following services:

1. **Marine litter assessment service** (provided by DFKI with OGS and MARIS).
2. **Zooscan taxonomic identification service** (provided by SU)
3. **Marine ecosystem monitoring service** (provided by EMSO, UPC, IFREMER, and MI)
4. **Oil spill detection service** (provided by CMCC and OrbitalEOS)
5. **Flowcam phytoplankton identification** (provided by VLIZ)

1.2 Metrics

For each operational installation, several metrics have been defined between the provider and WP5 leader, taking into account the following categories:

- Number of users – Number of unique users of the AI image processing service

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- Number of images – Number of images processed per year or Names of images ingested
- Number/names of the countries reached – the goal of this metric was to report how broadly the service is used and how the geographical coverage is changing with time.

The production metrics per installation are given in **Chapter 2** for the 2nd and 3rd project years. In the tables reference is made to the baseline, which is the situation per Use Case at the start of the iMagine project, based upon earlier activities. Also, some details about their final production configuration are given.

2 Installations

2.1 Marine litter assessment service

Description	This service supports ingestion, storage, analysis and processing of drone images, observing litter floating at surface waters in seas, rivers and lakes, and lying at beaches and shores, delivering standardised classified data sets, which are fit for purpose of environmental management and indicators.
Task	T5.1
URL	https://www.imagine-ai.eu/service/litter-assessment-service
Service Category	Thematic
Service Catalogue	Image Analysis Services for Aquatic Sciences
Providers	DFKI, MARIS, OGS
Location	Original service at DFKI - Germany
Modality of access	AI model and processing methodology available on the iMagine Marketplace
Support offered	Support of users and operation, including training of users
Operational since	near-operational since June - July 2024; full operational since September 2024

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User definition	Researchers from academics, monitoring agencies, NGO's, environmental management organisations
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2.1.1 Metrics

Metric name	Baseline	Define how measurement is done	M13–M24	M25–M36	TOTAL
Number of unique users of the AI image processing service	10	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	10	16	26
Number of images processed per year	1500	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	1	94	95 Explanation below in the Number of images processed per year section
Numbers of images ingested	200000	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	0	0 Explanation below in the Number of images processed per year section
Number of countries of users	7	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	1	2	3 Explanation below in the Number of countries section
Names of countries reached	Germany, Slovakia, BIH, Vietnam, Cambodia, The Philippines, Myanmar	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	Italy	Germany, Canada	

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2.1.2 Assessment

The service provides an operational environment at the iImagine platform for the detection and quantification of plastic litter floating on the water surface. It allows users to ingest drone footage of their area of interest to get back an analysis of the presence and count of litter items. The AI model and processing methodology are available on the iImagine Marketplace. In addition to providing inference for image classification, scripts were developed and made available that allow users to fine-tune the pre-trained models to their own data. The service utilises the OSCAR instance operated by iImagine as an inference service to invoke the model from an external application portal. The training datasets are published on Zenodo. The Deliverable D1.4 – Final Data Management Plan – gives more details about the publishing of training data sets as part of the iImagine project.

Explanation of the reported numbers in time:

Number of unique users of the AI image processing service

The presented numbers are a combination of users who were in contact with the service providers or got access through access requests, and unique cloners on git. The unique cloners in git are a snapshot of the past 14 days, recorded on the day the VA metrics were entered.

Number of images processed per year and images ingested:

The deviation from the target is caused by two factors:

1. The topic of UC1 is quite special, and necessitates pre-existing drone surveillance capabilities and adherence to rigorous image acquisition protocols. This limited the relevance to very specialised organisations with already high technical maturity.
2. The system analyses large images by automatically dividing them into small sections called 'tiles.' This removes the need for users to manually segment files. While the first project period focused on one large image, the second project period transitioned to analysing multiple individual tiles. Because some users processed these tiles on local hardware, their activity could not be tracked centrally, leading to incomplete metrics for this period.

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Number of countries:

Orthophotos and tiles from Italy, Germany, and Canada were analysed. Country information for users who used the models locally was not recorded. Due to the stringent technical requirements aforementioned, the geographic distribution of users was inherently restricted to regions with established drone-based monitoring capabilities. Consequently, it was not possible to meet the initial baseline for the 'Number of countries,' resulting in an underperformance relative to the projected geographic KPIs.

Corrective actions taken:

Throughout the project, the Use Case was promoted through the webinar series on 08 May 2025 to reach new audiences:

- [Webinar series page](#)
- [Webinar recording](#)

2.2 ZooScan image processing service

Description	ZooProcess is the image analytics pipeline for plankton images collected with the ZooScan instrument. The ZooScan is a commercial instrument, >150 units of which have been sold worldwide. It takes images of live or preserved zooplankton samples, crops and measurements and sends its data to EcoTaxa. EcoTaxa is a web application coupling a database with AI tools to accelerate the labelling of large quantities of plankton images by human operators, who are trained biologists but have no AI expertise. A significant time in the processing of ZooScan images is the manual separation of objects touching each other. Another is the correction of non-standard conformant metadata. Through iMagine, ZooProcess advanced through an improved interface and AI tools for segmentation, ported to the iMagine framework.
Task	T5.2
URL	https://www.imagine-ai.eu/service/zooprocess-service

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Service Category	Thematic
Service Catalogue	Image Analysis Services for Aquatic Sciences
Location	Currently: EGI + Villefranche-sur-mer, France, Ultimately: EGI + Distributed on the computers of ZooScan users
Modality of access	AI model and processing methodology available on the iMagine Marketplace. Dedicated ZooProcess software (with GUI) available from the website of the Plankton Imagery Platform of Villefranche-sur-mer.
Support offered	Training of users, assistance for data formatting for upload, assistance for data exploitation
Operational since	2010 for the initial version of ZooProcess; continuously improved since 10/2024 for the AI services from iMagine 08/2025 for the private beta of the new ZooProcess with a web UI calling the AI services
User definition	Scientific research groups (mostly used by technicians) + environment monitoring companies/agencies

2.2.1 Metrics

Metric name	Baseline	Define how measurement is done	M13-M24	M25-M36	TOTAL
Number of unique zooscan+zooproces users	~300 / y	no user tracking is available. We estimate >300 persons, from around the world since 150 ZooScans have been sold worldwide, all use ZooProcess, most are used by more than a single operator.	0	9	9 Explanation in the section below

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Number of scans (i.e. images) processed per year	~10000 / y	1 scan per working day, 150 zooscans => 10k scans	0	1,150	1,150 Explanation in the section below
Number of countries in which the current version of zooprocess is used	30	Number of countries in which a zooscan has been purchased	0	1	1 Explanation in the section below
Names of countries reached	France, Spain, Italy, Belgium, UK, Germany, etc. in the EU, Brazil, US, Canada, China, Japan, Korea	Countries in which a zooscan has been purchased	0	France	France

2.2.2 Assessment

To give more details on the software and services: the ZooProcess v10 accelerates the processing of images of plankton samples produced by the ZooScan instrument through the combined use of classical image segmentation and measurement methods with automated classification and panoptic segmentation by neural network models. This artificial intelligence approach allows the automatic separation of objects touching each other in the original image, to enable their exploitation in the future. The AI model and processing methodology are available on the iMagine Marketplace. The service utilises the OSCAR instance operated by iMagine as an inference service to invoke the model from ZooProcess, transparently for the user. The dataset was published on the SeaNoe platform, with a metadata record in Zenodo. The Deliverable D1.4 – Final Data Management Plan – gives more details about the publishing of training data sets as part of the iMagine project.

Explanation of the reported numbers in time:

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Number of unique zooscan+zooprocess users

Target underperformance is due to the lack of a mature GUI during the project period. While interest remained high, onboarding was limited to a technical subset capable of API integration. High consulting/download rates of the underlying dataset (250+ consultations) indicate latent demand that will be captured once the GUI is fully released.

Number of scans (i.e. images) processed per year

Reported metrics reflect only internal reprocessing of long-term time series (from 1966). Actual external usage could not be tracked due to the DEEPaaS API exposure mode in OSCAR, which bypassed the iImagine Grafana tracking dashboard.

Number of countries in which the current version of zooprocess is used

Global uptake was hindered by the GUI development timeline. Distribution remained concentrated among pilot partners and technical labs. Evidence of broader geographic interest is supported by external queries and dataset downloads, though these do not yet translate into 'active users' in the current tracking system.

Corrective actions taken:

Throughout the project, the Use Case was promoted through the webinar series on 16 January 2025 to reach new audiences:

- [Webinar series page](#)
- [Webinar recording](#)

Moreover, the Use Case took part in the [One Ocean Conference](#).

2.3 Marine ecosystem monitoring service

Description	This service is provided for the processing of video imagery, collected by cameras at EMSO underwater sites, identifying and further analysing interesting images for purposes of ecosystem monitoring. The service will be operated from
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	several EMSO sites where underwater videos are being collected. The three sites of this installation provide complementary capabilities for the whole pipeline of image collection, selection, AI-based analysis and annotation. EMSO–Obsea (UPC - SE) and EMSO–Azores (Ifremer – FR) have experience with using AI for the analysis of selected images for identification of biota. EMSO–SmartBay has experience with preselecting interesting images from the sizable video footage. Ifremer has experience with data management of EMSO raw and annotated imagery.
Task	T5.3
URL	https://www.imagine-ai.eu/case-study/ecosystem-monitoring-at-emso-sites-by-video-imagery
Service Category	Thematic
Service Catalogue	Image Analysis Services for Aquatic Sciences
Providers	UPC, IFREMER, MI,
Location	Vilanova i la Geltru coast (Barcelona, Spain) Lat. : 41° 10,93' N - Long. : 001° 45,15' E ; Lucky Strike (Azores) Lat. : 37° 17,60' N - Long.: 032° 16,40' W; Smartbay Observatory (Spiddal, Galway) Lat. : 53° 13,38' N - Long. : 09° 15,58' W
Modality of access	AI model and processing methodology available on the iMagine Marketplace.
Support offered	support and training
Operational since	September 2024
User definition	Researchers, monitoring agencies, NGOs, environmental management organisations.

2.3.1 EMSO–Azores metrics

Metric name	Baseline	Define how measurement is done	M13–M24	M25–M36	TOTAL
Number of user groups /	10	Account management of registered users and image	0	6	6 Explanation in the

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institutions accessing EMSO-Azores data (real time or data bank or images and multiparametric data)		processing runs by iMagine platform			related section below
Number of images generated and archived per year on the data bank	3000	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	N/A	N/A	N/A Explanation in the related section below
Number of countries of users	3	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	6	6
Names of countries reached	France, Italy, etc	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Netherlands, United States	

2.3.2 EMSO-SmartBay metrics

Metric name	Baseline	Define how measurement is done	M13-M24	M25-M36	TOTAL
Number of user groups / institutions accessing EMSO-Smartbay data (real time or data bank or images)	10	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	2	2 Explanation in the related section below

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and multiparametric data)					
Number of (Annotated) images generated and archived per year on the data bank	3000	Number of images Annotated for training datasets used by the Model Services	0	10,836	10,836
Number of images processed per year (by iMagine platform services)	0	Number of images processed per year by iMagine platform services are not available for modules deployed from the iMagine dashboard (Currently very small numbers of images have been processed by the initial users of the platform "guestimate" <100)	0	Not Available	Not Available Explanation in the related section below
Number of countries of users	3	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	1	1 Explanation in the related section below
Names of countries reached	France, Italy, etc	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	Ireland	Ireland

2.3.3 EMSO-Obsea metrics

Metric name	Baseline	Define how measurement is done	M13-M24	M25-M36	TOTAL
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Number of user groups / institutions accessing OBSEA data (real time or data bank or images and multiparametric data)	10	Number of dataset downloads (images with AI-based detections)	0	70	700
Number of images generated and archived per year on the data bank	3000	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	1.3M	1.3 M
Number of countries of users	3	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	N/A	N/A Explanation in the related section below
Names of countries reached	France, Italy, etc	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	Not Available as users are downloading from Zenodo	Not Available as users are downloading from Zenodo Explanation in the related section below

2.3.4 Assessment

UC3a – Azores:

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The Deep Sea Detection module was developed to provide an AI service for the automatic processing of images collected at the EMSO Azores underwater observatory, supporting the identification and analysis of fauna and habitats for ecosystem monitoring. It has been built on the DeepSeaSpy project, where citizen scientists annotated images of deep-sea habitats, and these annotations were used to train a YOLOv8 deep learning model. The module gives access to a pre-trained model, based on the DeepSeaSpy dataset, and to the possibility of adapting the workflow to other citizen science datasets. The dataset and trained models are openly shared on SeaNoe and Zenodo, while the module itself has been deployed on the iImagine marketplace for direct use. The Deliverable D1.4 – Final Data Management Plan – gives more details about the publishing of training data sets as part of the iImagine project. Comprehensive documentation is also provided in the GitHub repository to guide users in running and adapting the pipeline.

Usage during the production period:

Number of unique users of the AI image processing service:

From M13 to M24, the Deep Sea Detection service was still in preparation, and no usage was reported. Between M25 and M36, activity became visible mainly through dataset and code access. The indicators collected for this period include 74 dataset downloads, 1 dataset reuse (with no citation found at this stage), 2 institutional users (not using the iImagine platform) and around 6 GitHub cloners.

Number of images processed per year:

The number of processed images could not be reported, as activity was measured through dataset access and Github repository usage rather than platform statistics.

Number of countries:

In terms of geographical reach, dataset downloads between M25 and M36 came from six countries—France, Germany, Italy, Poland, the Netherlands, and the United States—since country information is only available from dataset download metrics through SEANOE.

Overall, the project shows emerging use through dataset downloads, a first reuse, institutional users outside the iImagine platform, and activity on GitHub, while the operational module on iImagine has not yet attracted users but may do so in the future. These figures are based on multiple sources, including Seanoe and Zenodo downloads, institutional user logs, GitHub traffic, and Google Scholar

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citations. A monitoring process will also be established to track future citations of dataset DOIs in scientific publications, providing further evidence of impact.

UC3s – Smartbay:

EMSO Smartbay developed and deployed 3 AI Computer Services on the iMagine platform [Smartbay Species Detection](#), [Smartbay Marine Types](#) for usage on Smartbay underwater imagery and video and [Smartbay prawn Burrow detection](#) for prawn burrow detection in underwater towed camera imagery and video for use in assisting Prawn Fishery surveys. The services use YOLOv8 models. Smartbay also briefly investigated a Video Quality Assessment model (DOVER VQA), for scoring video quality, but staffing resource and time issues prevented the further investigation and development of an AI service based on the model.

EMSO-Smartbay relied on Summer Bursor students in 2024 and 2025 to annotate images for the creation of Nephrop(Prawn) Burrow, Marine Species and Marine Types Training Datasets. Datasets were annotated in an on-premise [CVAT](#) Instance and model training was mainly carried out in the Marine Institute using an on-premise GPU and Jupyter notebook environment to develop in-house capabilities. The [MLFlow](#) Instance on the iMagine platform was used in a number of training runs for gathering model training metrics.

It is intended to also deploy the models in on-premise, container infrastructure for use on the smartbay video Multi-year archive (Continuously recorded 2-minute video files) to identify interesting video footage in the archive and also species detection on real time video feeds. The Nephrops burrow detection model will be trialled further on Nephrops Fisheries surveys. The developed models have been used in-house to test semi-automatic annotation of imagery in CVAT.

The outputs and workflows developed in the iMagine project have generated further interest with work continuing on enhancing the Nephrop burrow training dataset and the detection model and also working further on tracking and counting burrows in Survey Imagery. The Marine Types and Species training datasets will hopefully continue to be added to and further work has begun on crab species training datasets for work in crab fishery surveys, these annotations will be also used to further enhance the smartbay species detection models. The Deliverable D1.4 – Final Data Management Plan – gives more details about the publishing of training data sets as part of the iMagine project.

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Usage during the production period:

Number of unique users of the AI image processing service:

- For EMSO-Smartbay(Marine Institute) currently 2 groups of users in the Marine Institute have used the AI services deployed on the iMagine Platform (Marine Institute Smartbay Team and Marine Institute Nephrops survey team).
- EMSO Smartbay saw a total of 116 Training dataset downloads from Zenodo to September 2025 (55 Smartbay Marine Species Training dataset, 45 Smartbay Marine Types Training dataset, 16 Smartbay Nephrops Burrow training dataset downloads). Apart from the numbers of downloads, Zenodo does not provide further download user metrics (e.g. Country of download etc.)
- EMSO Smartbay saw a total of 118 Docker Hub container Downloads, to September 2025, (These would be the Smartbay iMagine service container images on Docker Hub)

Number of images processed per year:

- For EMSO-Smartbay(Marine Institute) over 10,000 images were annotated and incorporated into the Training datasets, used for the Models and services.
- EMSO-Smartbay deployed 3 Object detection services on the iMagine platform, the number of images/video submitted to the service modules deployed from the iMagine dashboard are not currently tracked by the deployed modules or the iMagine platform (this metric would require logging HTTP API calls submitting images to the iMagine services images either by the platform or modules themselves).
- For EMSO-Smartbay a small number of images have been submitted to the deployed services on the iMagine platform by the initial internal Smartbay and Marine Institute users of the model Services.
- For EMSO-Smartbay the Nephrop Burrow Model has also been used onsite (in the Marine Institute) to test detection and assist in the semi-automatic annotation of new Prawn Survey imagery and will be used to help speed up training dataset additions in an in-house instance of CVAT.

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Number of countries:

- For EMSO-Smartbay (Marine Institute) 1 country (Ireland) has used the Smartbay Services on the Imagine Platform. The Model services have been used internally by Smartbay staff and Marine Institute Nephrops fisheries staff
- For EMSO-Smartbay further development and improvement of the initial Models is expected to increase interest in the models and Training datasets for Countries bordering the North East Atlantic Ocean.

UC3o – OBSEA:

The OBSEA is an underwater observatory. Over the years different cameras have been deployed, having a vast archival of pictures starting from 2011. AI techniques are used to automate the detection and classification of the fish specimens captured by the cameras at OBSEA and provide a timeseries of fish detections. This data can be easily processed by scientists who can spend their time doing actual science instead of counting fish picture by picture. Standards have been developed for managing and storing video imagery, and annotated images have been developed. The workflow has been set up in the iImagine AI Platform using artificial intelligence to preselect interesting images and analyse selected images for the identification of biota. Documentation and guidance about standard data management practices and the use of AI analysis pipelines for biota classification have also been developed. The Deliverable D1.4 – Final Data Management Plan – gives more details about the publishing of training data sets as part of the iImagine project.

Usage during the production period:

Number of unique users of the AI image processing service:

In the EMSO-Obsea use case the images were pre-processed, so final users are only accessing scientific datasets published at Zenodo.

Number of images processed per year:

In EMSO-Obsea use case, during the project lifetime a total of 1.3 million pictures were produced and analyzed. Thus a mean of 433k pics / year were processed.

Number of countries:

Zenodo (main dataset delivery platform) does not provide geographic information on users / data downloads.

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Corrective actions:

Throughout the project, the 3 Use Cases were promoted through the webinar series to reach new audiences:

- 30 April 2025:
 - [Webinar series page](#)
 - [Webinar recording](#)
- 22 May 2025:
 - [Webinar series page](#)
 - [Webinar recording](#)
- 26 February 2025:
 - [Webinar series page](#)
 - [Webinar recording](#)

Moreover, the Use Case took part in the following events:

- [Blue-Cloud 2026 webinar](#)
- [OCEANS 2025 conference](#)
- [MARTECH Workshop 2025](#)
- [IMDIS2024 conference](#)
- [ANERIS Workshop on AI Basics for Image Processing](#)

2.4 Oil spill detection service

Description	WITOIL (Where Is the Oil) was developed to support emergency management during oil spill accidents. As a Digital Twin system, it combines near real-time input data from environmental models, simulation, and analysis, providing tools to predict and manage complex scenarios effectively. Through WITOIL-for-iMagine, the service leveraged the DEEPaaS API and the Medslik-II model to simulate the transport and weathering of actual or hypothetical oil slicks. The use of
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	Bayesian optimization further enhanced Medslik-II's predictive accuracy as a test case based on the satellite imagery provided by OrbitalEOS and pushed into Zenodo by University of Trento. Witoil for iMagine relies on ECMWF (ERA5 reanalysis) wind fields and CMEMS ocean currents and sea surface temperature to reproduce spill dispersion, while users specify spill parameters. The resulting outputs include spatial-temporal distributions of oil concentration on the sea surface.
Task	T5.4
URL	https://www.imagine-ai.eu/service/witoil-service
Service Category	Thematic
Service Catalogue	Image Analysis Services for Aquatic Sciences
Providers	CMCC, University of Trento, OrbitalEOS
Location	Via Marco Biagi, 5, 73100 Lecce LE (Italy)
Modality of access	AI model and processing methodology available on the iMagine Marketplace.
Support offered	Support of users and simulations, including training of users
Operational since	October 2024
User definition	researchers from academics, monitoring agencies, NGO's, environmental management organisations

2.4.1 Metrics

Metric name	Baseline	Define how measurement is done	M13-M24	M25-M36	TOTAL
Number of unique users of the AI image processing	100	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	80	80 Explanation in the related

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service					section below
Number of images processed per year	1000	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	172	172 Explanation in the related section below
Number of images ingested	200	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	172	172 Explanation in the related section below
Number of countries of users	10	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	N/A – User location is not tracked in the iMagine platform	NA
Names of countries reached	France, Italy, etc	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	0	N/A	NA

2.4.2 Assessment

WITOIL (Where Is the Oil) is a multi-model Decision Support System (DSS) on-demand service that forecasts transport and weathering of actual or hypothetical oil spills in the global, regional European Seas, and in the selected coastal areas. WITOIL uses the MEDSLIK-II oil spill model forced by operational meteo-oceanographic services. The service has been further refined by using labelled image datasets from Sentinel 1, Sentinel 2 and Landsat 8 satellites to improve existing deep-learning algorithms and the AI-supported detection of oil spills. WITOIL is now an operational service in the iMagine-AI platform and interfaces with existing operational marine pollution oil spill monitoring and modelling services running at CMCC. Relevant guidelines and documentation are also available to

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promote the service uptake. The system is accessible through a simple user interface (either through Swagger API or GradIO) all within the iImagine marketplace, so a less experienced user can perform simulations on their own without the need for extensive computing skills. The Deliverable D1.4 – Final Data Management Plan – gives more details about the publishing of training data sets as part of the iImagine project.

Usage during the production period:

Number of unique users of the AI image processing service

There were 9 Git clones in the last 14 days in the Git repository. There were 6 unique visitors and a total of 17 views in the Git repository over the last 14 days. These numbers represent only a small percentage of the total number of visits and clones, however that is the limit github allows us to see past activity.

Number of images processed per year and images ingested:

There were a total of 49 downloads and 211 views of the dataset 'iMAGINE UC4 – Segmented Oil Spills', as available in the Zenodo database.

Number of countries:

The small size of the oil spill community and our focus on scientific correctness limited the overall user numbers. Furthermore, country-specific tracking was not part of the technical design, so geographic metrics could not be fully captured. The sources available for measuring traffic metrics do not dispose of country tracking.

Corrective actions:

Throughout the project, the Use Case was promoted through the webinar series on 16 January 2025 to reach new audiences:

- [Webinar series page](#)
- [Webinar recording](#)

Moreover, the Use Case took part in the [EGU 2025](#).

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2.5 Flowcam phytoplankton identification

Description	This service supports image-based taxonomic identification of plankton particles in the micro-plankton size range (including photosynthetic plankton or phytoplankton). As part of the service a long-term dataset of over 1.4 million expert validated plankton images is being made available to serve as a high-quality training dataset for new AI supported plankton identification. Enabling access to both the dataset and the analytical algorithms from the iImagine AI framework will support additional users to set up and run their own plankton image recognition pipeline.
Task	T5.5
URL	https://www.imagine-ai.eu/service/phytoplankton-identification-service
Service Category	Thematic
Service Catalogue	Image Analysis Services for Aquatic Sciences
Location	Original service at VLIZ - Belgium
Modality of access	AI model and processing methodology available on the iImagine Marketplace.
Support offered	Support of users and operation, including training of users
Operational since	July 2024
User definition	Single researchers, environmental management organisations

2.5.1 Metrics

Metric name	Baseline	Define how measurement is done	M13-M24	M25-M36	TOTAL
Number of unique users of the AI image processing service	5	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iImagine platform + internal and affiliated user count	7	122	129

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Number of images processed per year	300,000	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform + internal and affiliated user count	2,075,958	185,412	2,261,370
Number of images ingested	1,400,000	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform + internal and affiliated user count	2,075,958	185,412	2,261,370
Number of countries of users	1	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	7	3	10
Names of countries reached	Belgium, France, Spain etc	Account management of registered users and image processing runs by iMagine platform	France, Italy, Belgium, Germany, Spain, The Netherlands and Ireland	Taiwan, the United States, and Greenland	France, Italy, Belgium, Germany, Spain, The Netherlands, Ireland, Taiwan, the United States, and Greenland,

2.5.2 Assessment

The Flowcam phytoplankton identification service leverages a deep learning image recognition algorithm based on a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to analyze FlowCam image data stored in the institute's internal MongoDB database for phytoplankton taxonomy. The output data adheres to FAIR principles, following Darwin Core standards and relevant vocabularies, ensuring interoperability, accessibility, and long-term usability. The service is hosted on the iMagine-AI platform, which provides a fully operational environment for processing images, storing output data, and supplying guidance and documentation to users. High-quality phytoplankton image datasets accumulated over more than four years are available for research, analysis, and further model

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development. Users can employ the service to determine the taxonomic composition of phytoplankton samples. The platform supports reuse of pre-trained models or fine-tuning on new models for taxonomic identification. The Deliverable D1.4 – Final Data Management Plan – gives more details about the publishing of training data sets as part of the iMagine project.

The service is deployed through a combination of methods to meet diverse user needs: the Marketplace Inference Service performs automated inference on submitted images; the OSCAR Inference Service provides an intuitive interface for performing inference while tracking usage metrics; and the Train Your Own CNN option allows users to train custom models on their own datasets using the platform's infrastructure. Overall, this deployment enables efficient, scalable, and traceable AI-based analysis of FlowCam phytoplankton images, supporting both operational monitoring and broader research applications across multiple institutions and countries.

Usage during the production period:

Number of unique users of the AI image processing service:

- At the start of the reporting period, the Flowcam phytoplankton identification service had a baseline of five registered users, composed of internal staff and affiliated researchers. Initial usage supported ongoing projects such as LifeWatch and Jerico-Next/S3, with only a small number of users actively submitting images.
- During months 6–12, usage grew slightly as the service supported two internal and two affiliated users. By months 13–24 (M13–M24), the number of unique users increased to seven, reflecting additional internal and affiliated personnel as well as a high school teacher testing the OSCAR inference system.
- The period between months 25–36 (M25–M36) saw a substantial surge, with 122 new users joining. This growth was driven by new access requests via iMagine Services, international collaborators at the Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Research and the Greenland Institute of Natural Resources, and technical workshops using dummy annotated datasets. By the end of the reporting period, the total number of unique users reached 129, highlighting the scalability and adoption of the service across research, educational, and international contexts.

Number of images processed per year:

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- At baseline, the service processed approximately 300,000 images per year. During the monitoring period, image processing volumes increased dramatically due to both internal operations and external users leveraging the platform.
- In months 13–24 (M13–M24), a total of 2,075,958 images were processed. This figure includes images processed for ongoing monitoring projects as well as contributions from PhD students. In months 25–36 (M25–M36), an additional 185,412 images were processed, bringing the cumulative total to 2,261,370 images.

Number of countries:

- Initially, the service was used by researchers at the kick-off workshop (7): France, Italy, Belgium, Germany, Spain, The Netherlands and Ireland. Over time, the geographic reach expanded through workshops, international collaborations, and institutional access requests.
- In months 25–36, three additional countries gained access, including Taiwan, the United States, and Greenland, resulting in a total of **10 countries** represented